

Supporting Information

ARPIP: Ancestral sequence Reconstruction with insertions and deletions under the Poisson Indel Process

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Appendix 1

The PIP description

Insertion Probability.— For every node $v \in V$, the probability of inserting a single character on edge $e = (v \rightarrow pa(v))$ is proportional to the branch length $b(v)$:

$$\iota(v) = \frac{1}{\|\tau\| + \mu^{-1}} \cdot \begin{cases} b(v) & \text{if } v \neq \Omega \\ \mu^{-1} & \text{if } v = \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\|\tau\|$ is the sum of all branch lengths (total tree length).

Survival probability.— The survival probability $\beta(v)$ for a character inserted along edge e is given by:

$$\beta(v) = \begin{cases} (1 - \exp(-\mu b(v))) / (\mu b(v)) & \text{if } v \neq \Omega \\ 1 & \text{if } v = \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Pure survival probability.— To compute the probability that a character inserted before edge e survives along edge e , we define the pure survival probability $\zeta(v) = \exp(-\mu b(v))$ associated with node v . Likewise, the probability that the character will not survive along the edge is $1 - \zeta(v)$. The pure survival probability $\zeta(v)$ differs from the definition of $\beta(v)$ with regard to the insertion location. While in $\zeta(v)$ the character is already present at $pa(v)$, in $\beta(v)$ the character is inserted in a random location along the edge associated with v . In both cases, however, the character is required to survive until node v (Maiolo, 2019).

MSA column probability.— For each individual MSA column m , the probability $p(m)$ is defined by marginalizing over all possible homology paths that may have created that MSA column:

$$p(m) = \sum_{v \subset V} \iota(v) f_v, \quad (3)$$

where f_v denotes the probability of all possible homology paths for MSA column m and the subtree rooted at v . Note that f_v can be zero for some nodes, namely the ones where an insertion is impossible given the data in m .

The probability of all possible homology paths.—

$$f_v = \begin{cases} \mathbb{1}[v \in \mathcal{A}] \beta(v) \sum_{\sigma \in \Sigma} \pi_\varepsilon(\sigma) \tilde{f}_v(\sigma) & \text{if } m \neq m_\emptyset \\ 1 - \beta(v) + \beta(v) \sum_{\sigma \in \Sigma} \pi_\varepsilon(\sigma) \tilde{f}_v(\sigma) & \text{o.w.,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where m_\emptyset is MSA column full of gaps and

$$\tilde{f}_v(\sigma) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{1}[m_v = \sigma] & \text{if } v \in \mathcal{L} \\ \prod_{w \in \text{child}(v)} \left[\sum_{\sigma' \in \Sigma_\varepsilon} \exp(b(w) Q_\varepsilon)_{(\sigma, \sigma')} \tilde{f}_w(\sigma') \right] & \text{o.w.,} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

and $\mathbb{1}[\cdot]$ is the indicator function. The recursive function $\tilde{f}_v(\sigma)$ denotes the partial likelihood of a single character under the substitution-deletion events.

Appendix 2

Detailed description of IndelPoints algorithm

The goal of the IndelPoints algorithm is to find the combination of insertion and deletion points with the highest conditional probability for a given site. These indel points define a homology path which is the best possible explanation of the homologous characters in the alignment. We infer these indel points using a greedy progressive approach, finding the homology path with the highest conditional probability in each node of the tree and progressively extending the path at other nodes. This way, for a given site

we find the best partial homology path at each tree node, and can select the best homology path on the whole tree once we reach the root.

The space of possible homology paths is constrained by the definition of PIP, meaning that per site there can only be a single insertion location and multiple deletions. Moreover, the sets of nodes that are possible insertion and deletion locations are non-overlapping. A homology path will have a non-zero conditional probability if and only if it explains the full site in the alignment, i.e. it contains one of the nodes $v \in \mathcal{A}$ as an insertion location. This means that in any node that is not a possible insertion location the conditional probability can always be set to 0.

Based on the properties of PIP, we can describe the evaluation separately for possible deletion nodes and for all other nodes in the tree. The set \mathcal{G} of potential deletion locations defines the root nodes of subtrees that went extinct at the leaves. For simplicity we will call these nodes extinction nodes. For each of these nodes, we will find the set of deletion nodes with the highest conditional probability and will set the conditional probability of the full homology path to 0. We will call the complementary set of nodes $v \notin \mathcal{G}$ the set of survival nodes. In these nodes, the character either got inserted along the branch $\text{pa}(v) \rightarrow v$ for $v \in \mathcal{A}$, or got inserted in an ancestor of v for $v \notin \mathcal{A}$. In either case the character definitely survived until v .

We traverse the tree in post order, evaluating possible homology paths per tree node. The algorithm is described separately for the two node sets (extinction nodes and survival nodes) however all necessary computation can be done in a single tree traversal. It is important to note that here the values are computed at the highest point of the branch $\text{pa}(v) \rightarrow v$ rather than at the bottom of the branch leading to v . To simplify notation, we will use v_L and v_R to denote the left and right child node of v respectively.

Evaluating extinction nodes.— For each extinction node $v \in \mathcal{G}$ we set the insertion node to none ($\mathcal{I}_v = \emptyset$) and consequently the probability of the best global homology path to 0 ($p_v = 0$).

We need to learn whether the deletion was more likely along the branch leading to v or more likely in the child subtrees. The character could have gone extinct before reaching node v , which is the probability of deletion happening along the branch $\text{pa}(v) \rightarrow v$. Moreover, if v is a leaf ($v \in \mathcal{L}$), we can certainly state that it is the current best deletion node ($\mathcal{D}_v = v$) and that f_v at that node represents the certain deletion ($f_v = 1 - \zeta(v)$, extinction probability). On the other hand, if the node v is not a leaf node ($v \notin \mathcal{L}$), we compare the deletion probability at $\text{pa}(v) \rightarrow v$, $1 - \zeta(v)$, with the product of survival along $\text{pa}(v) \rightarrow v$ and subsequent deletion at or below nodes v_R and v_L , $f_{v_R} f_{v_L} \zeta(v)$. Among the two, we select the value that represents the best scenario and set f_v and \mathcal{D}_v appropriately ($f_v = 1 - \zeta(v)$ and $\mathcal{D}_v = \{v\}$ or $f_v = f_{v_R} f_{v_L} \zeta(v)$ and $\mathcal{D}_v = \{\mathcal{D}_{v_R} \cup \mathcal{D}_{v_L}\}$ respectively).

The pseudocode for extinction node evaluation is shown in Algorithm 1, and the corresponding flowchart is available in the supplemental materials (see Fig. S.1).

Figure S. 1: Evaluating extinction nodes algorithm, where \mathcal{H}_v defines the homology path of node v , f_v is the probability of that homology path and p_v is the probability of the best homology path. \mathcal{I}_v is the set of possible insertion points while \mathcal{D}_v is the set of all possible deletion points for node v . $\zeta(v)$ denotes the pure survival probability of node v . Moreover, \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{L} represent the set of potential deletion points and leaves, respectively.

Algorithm 1: Evaluating extinction nodes.

Input: Phylogenetic tree τ
Output: Homology path with the highest probability $\mathcal{H}(m)$

```
for  $\forall v \in \mathcal{G}$  do
   $p_v = 0$ ;
  if  $v \in \mathcal{L}$  then
     $f_v = 1 - \zeta(v)$ ;
     $\mathcal{H}_v = \{\mathcal{I}_v = \emptyset, \mathcal{D}_v = \{v\}\}$ ;
  else
    if  $\zeta(v)f_{v_R}f_{v_L} < 1 - \zeta(v)$  then
       $f_v = 1 - \zeta(v)$ ;
       $\mathcal{H}_v = \{\mathcal{I}_v = \emptyset, \mathcal{D}_v = \{v\}\}$ ;
    else
       $f_v = \zeta(v)f_{v_R}f_{v_L}$ ;
       $\mathcal{H}_v = \{\mathcal{I}_v = \emptyset, \mathcal{D}_v = \mathcal{D}_{v_R} \cup \mathcal{D}_{v_L}\}$ ;
    end
  end
end
end
```

Evaluating survival nodes.— All nodes $v \notin \mathcal{G}$ are definite survival nodes – meaning that the character survived along the branch $\text{pa}(v) \rightarrow v$. We distinguish two types of survival nodes, $v \in \mathcal{A}$ (potential insertion nodes) and $v \notin \mathcal{A}$, nodes where an insertion could not have happened. $v \notin \mathcal{A}$ is the simpler one, as the homology path at such nodes will not have an associated insertion node, while a full homology path needs to have an insertion. This means that for all such nodes the probability of a homology path will be 0 ($p_v = 0$) and the set of insertion nodes will be empty ($\mathcal{I}_v = \emptyset$). In case $v \in \mathcal{A}$, we compute the non-zero homology path probability according to the formulas defined for PIP, $p_v = \iota(v)\beta(v)$ for a leaf node and $p_v = \iota(v)\beta(v)f_{v_R}f_{v_L}$ for an internal node. We also set $\mathcal{I}_v = v$, representing a possible insertion at this node. While the set \mathcal{A} may contain multiple nodes, an instance of a homology path can only have a single insertion location. This implies that when we compute the probability of a homology path for a node $v \in \mathcal{A}$, we essentially assume that it is the only possible insertion location while all other nodes are treated as regular nodes in the tree.

The conditional probability of survival is independent of whether v is a potential insertion node or not. If the node is a leaf ($v \in \mathcal{L}$), the character will have certainly survived, thus $f_v = \zeta(v)$, and the deletion node set is empty $\mathcal{D}_v = \emptyset$. On the other hand, if v is an internal node, we need to account for the survival along branch $\text{pa}(v) \rightarrow v$ and propagate any possible deletion nodes that were already selected, thus $f_v = f_{v_R} f_{v_L} \zeta(v)$ and $\mathcal{D}_v = \mathcal{D}_{v_R} \cup \mathcal{D}_{v_L}$.

Reaching the root of the tree Ω , we will have processed all the nodes in the tree and computed the probabilities of the homology paths conditioned on the insertion point at each node. These probabilities will only be non-zero for nodes $v \in \mathcal{A}$, which allows us to choose the best homology path simply as $\mathcal{H}_{\arg \max(p_v)}$ – the homology path corresponding to the node with the highest probability. We then extract the subtree τ_m rooted at $\mathcal{I}_{\arg \max(p_v)}$ and pruned at $\mathcal{D}_{\arg \max(p_v)}$ from the tree τ .

The pseudocode for survival node evaluation is presented in Algorithm 2 and the corresponding flowchart is available in the supplemental materials (see Fig. S.2).

Figure S. 2: Evaluating survival nodes algorithm, \mathcal{H}_v defines the homology path of node v represents by the set of possible insertion points \mathcal{I}_v and the set of all possible deletion points \mathcal{D}_v . Moreover, f_v is the probability of that homology path while p_v is the probability of the best homology path. $\iota(v)$, $\beta(v)$ and $\zeta(v)$ are respectively insertion, survival and pure survival probabilities at node v . \mathcal{A} represents the set of potential insertion points and \mathcal{L} shows the set of leaves.

Algorithm 2: Evaluating survival nodes

Input: Phylogenetic tree τ

Output: Homology path with the highest conditional probability $\mathcal{H}(m)$

```
for  $\forall v \notin \mathcal{G}$  do
  if  $v \in \mathcal{L}$  then
     $p_v = \mathbb{1}[v \in \mathcal{A}] \iota(v) \beta(v)$ ;
     $f_v = \zeta(v)$ ;
     $\mathcal{H}_v = \{\mathcal{I}_v = \mathbb{1}[v \in \mathcal{A}]v, \mathcal{D}_v = \emptyset\}$ ;
  else
     $p_v = \mathbb{1}[v \in \mathcal{A}] \iota(v) \beta(v) f_{v_R} f_{v_L}$ ;
     $f_v = \zeta(v) f_{v_R} f_{v_L}$ ;
     $\mathcal{H}_v = \{\mathcal{I}_v = \mathbb{1}[v \in \mathcal{A}]v, \mathcal{D}_v = \mathcal{D}_{v_R} \cup \mathcal{D}_{v_L}\}$ ;
  end
end
return  $\mathcal{H}_{\arg \max(p_v)}$ ;
```

Appendix 3

Detailed DP joint ASR under PIP

Similar to how it is done in FastML (Pupko et al., 2000), we reconstruct the ancestral characters in two consecutive steps. First, we compute the likelihoods using dynamic programming (DP), and then use the precomputed values for joint ASR. However, instead of reconstructing the ancestral states on the whole tree τ , we work on the subtree τ_m extracted using the most likely indel history for the site m under PIP model.

DP likelihood computation.— In the forward phase, as in Pupko’s ASR method, we traverse the tree τ_m in post-order. While visiting each internal node v , we compute the likelihood $\text{Lk}_v(i)$ and the corresponding best ancestral character state $\text{CS}_v(i)$ for each character i in the alphabet ($i \in \Sigma$). We assume that the best ASR in a subtree rooted at the node v is independent of the rest of the tree. $\text{Lk}_v(i)$ is the likelihood of the best reconstruction on this subtree conditioned on the parent of node v has the character i at that site. And $\text{CS}_v(i)$ is the character state assigned to node v in this optimal conditional reconstruction.

To compute the likelihood values and the corresponding candidate character states, we have to determine whether a node is a leaf or not. Let j be the observed character at v . If $v \in \mathcal{L}$, we assign $\text{CS}_v(i) = j$ and the likelihood value is $\text{Lk}_v(i) = P_{ij}(v)$, where $P(v) = \exp(b(v) \cdot Q_\varepsilon)$ is the transition probability matrix along the branch $\text{pa}(v) \rightarrow v$. If a node v is not a leaf ($v \notin \mathcal{L}$), we compute the likelihood value and the candidate characters for all the non-root internal nodes based on the values already computed in its children. For each $i \in \Sigma$ the likelihood value is $\text{Lk}_v(i) = \max_j(P_{ij}(v) \cdot \text{Lk}_{v_L}(j) \cdot \text{Lk}_{v_R}(j))$ and the candidate character is the value of j producing the previous maximization $\text{CS}_v(i) = \arg \max_j(P_{ij}(v) \cdot \text{Lk}_{v_L}(j) \cdot \text{Lk}_{v_R}(j))$. We compute these values until all the nodes have been visited except for the root. While visiting the root, the likelihood is computed slightly differently as the transition probabilities are replaced with the alphabet equilibrium frequencies $\pi_{\varepsilon i}$, $\text{Lk}_v(i) = \pi_{\varepsilon i} \cdot \text{Lk}_{v_L}(i) \cdot \text{Lk}_{v_R}(i)$. Since the root has no possible ancestors, we define the single candidate character state as $\text{CS}_\Omega = \arg \max_i(\text{Lk}_\Omega)$. The pseudocode of the algorithm is shown in Algorithm 3.

Joint ASR.— After computing the likelihoods of all potential ancestral characters, we traverse the tree in pre-order from the root of the tree τ_m to select the single most likely ancestral character per node A_v . We assign the most likely character state at the root by picking the character i that maximizes the likelihood value $\text{CS}_{\Omega_{\tau_m}} = \arg \max_i(\text{Lk}_v)$. For all other internal nodes in the traversal we assign $\text{CS}_v(A_{\text{pa}(v)})$ as the best reconstruction (for example if the state reconstructed for the parent of v is proline ($i = \text{P}$), the ancestral state of v will be $\text{CS}_v(i = \text{P})$). We continue the process until the most likely character is assigned at all the internal nodes. The formula is presented below where Ω_{τ_m} is the root of subtree τ_m :

$$A_v = \begin{cases} \text{CS}_v(\arg \max(\text{Lk}_v)) & v = \Omega_{\tau_m} \\ \text{CS}_v(A_{\text{pa}(v)}) & \text{o.w.} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Algorithm 3: Computing the likelihood

Input: Phylogenetic subtree τ_m

MSA column m

Extended substitution model Q_ϵ

Extended equilibrium frequencies π_ϵ

Output: Likelihood array of node v Lk_v

Candidate character array of node v with ML values CS_v

$\Omega_{\tau_m} =$ root of subtree τ_m ;

$P(v) = \exp(b(v) \cdot Q_\epsilon)$;

if $v \in \mathcal{L}$ **then**

$j =$ observed character at v ;

for $\forall i \in \Sigma$ **do**

$CS_v(i) = j$;

$Lk_v(i) = P_{ij}(v)$;

end

else

$v_L =$ left child node;

$v_R =$ right child node;

if v is equal to Ω_{τ_m} **then**

for $\forall i \in \Sigma$ **do**

$Lk_v(i) = \pi_{\epsilon i} \cdot Lk_{v_L}(i) \cdot Lk_{v_R}(i)$;

end

$CS_\Omega = \arg \max_i(Lk_v)$;

else

for $i \in \Sigma$ **do**

for $j \in \Sigma$ **do**

$S(j)^\ddagger = P_{ij}(v) \cdot Lk_{v_L}(j) \cdot Lk_{v_R}(j)$;

end

$Lk_v(i) = \max(S)$;

$CS_v(i) = \arg \max_j(S)$;

end

end

end

REFERENCES

REFERENCES

- Maiolo, M. 2019. Progressive Multiple Sequence Alignment with Indel Evolution. Ph.D. thesis University of Lausanne Lausanne PhD thesis.
- Pupko, T., I. Pe, R. Shamir, and D. Graur. 2000. A fast algorithm for joint reconstruction of ancestral amino acid sequences. *Molecular biology and evolution* 17:890–896.

Supplement figures

Figure S. 3: Illustration of the rooted *Betacoronavirus* phylogenetic tree reconstructed by PhyML 3.0 from the PRANK alignment. Note that the original tree was unrooted which ARPIP used mid-point rooting method to make the tree rooted.

Figure S. 4: A snippet from the *CoV* dataset containing the MSA inferred by PRANK and the ancestor sequences predicted by ARPIP and FastML. The tree is obtained by PhyML 3.0, shown in Figure S. 3. Note that FastML algorithm works on an unrooted tree which, compared to ARPIP, resulted in one fewer internal sequence reconstructed (due to the absence of the root node).